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SOME GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING

Annontatsion : *Language plays an important role in our everyday life interactions. It is used by human to do communication with other people in conveying and sharing idea, feeling, emotion, and information both in spoken and written forms. It also serves the human needs in their everyday communication in any situation. Language is classified into 3 types, namely: first language, second language and foreign language. First language is the language that a person has learnt from birth or within the critical period, or that a person speaks the best and so is often the basis for sociolinguistic identity.*

First language is also called mother language, native language or L1. Second language is a language that is not the mother tongue, but that is used for public communication. In other words second language is a non-native language officially recognized and adopted in a multilingual country as a means of public communication. Foreign language is a language indigenous to another country. It is also a language not spoken in the native country of the person referred to. The differences between first language and second language are: first language is learned by a child at home usually from their parents. It is typically acquired at the crucial period of cognitive development; pre-puberty, when L1 and other crucial life-skills are also acquired or learned. Second language is learnt by a child after he/she gets his/her first language. It is not learned as part of the learner's general cognitive development. It is not an essential life-skill in the same way that the L1 is.¹

English is studied in some countries as second language or foreign language. It becomes a problem because of the position of English as a second language or foreign language still a strange material for a learner, so, the mastery of its language still contain many obstacle. Because of it, in English teaching learning process should be beginning with a new second language vocabulary taught. It will make learner easier to learn English as second language or foreign language. Learning as a process is a collaboration of effort orchestrated from three focal points—the student, the teacher, and the learning context. A principle is a suggested pathway to organize the activities from these three functional points so that the optimization of learning is guaranteed. If anybody follows the path, the likelihood of (effective) learning to happen is very high. A tentative pathway gets the title of a principle only if it is functionally replicable in all

intended contexts. A principle warrants universal application only if evidence-based results ensuing from repeated random trials affirms its infallibility. The general model for introducing new language, which gives, and overall picture of the procedure.

The model has five components:

- 1) lead-in,
- 2) elicitation,
- 3) explanation,
- 4) accurate reproduction
- 5) immediate creativity.

During the lead-in, the context is introduced and the meaning or use of the new language is demonstrated. This is the stage at which students may hear or see some language (including the new language) and during which students may become aware of certain key concepts. The key concepts are those pieces of information about the context that are vital if students are to understand the context and thus the meaning and use of the new language. If we are introducing a dialogue in which a visitor to a town is asking for directions from a local resident it will be necessary for the students to understand that:

- The speaker is a stranger.
- He or she doesn't know where something is.
- He or she is talking to someone who lives in the town.

With this knowledge the students will understand what the speaker is saying (and why) in the following dialogue:

Visitor: Excuse me!

Resident: Yes?

Visitor: Where's the station?

Resident: It's opposite the hospital at the end of this street.

Visitor: Thank you very much.

Resident: Don't mention it.

In the case of formulated information (such as the airline timetable) it will be necessary for students to understand the concepts of destination, via, departure and arrival, for without these they will not understand the meaning of such sentences as 'Flight 309 goes to Paris'. During the lead-in stage the teacher can also demonstrate the probable course of an interaction (particularly at more advanced levels). Thus, at this stage we introduce our context (making sure that key concepts are understood) and show the new language in use².

During the elicitation stage, the teacher tries to see if the students can produce the new language. If they can it would clearly be wasteful and de-motivating for them if a lot of time were spent practicing the language that they already know. At the elicitation stage – depending on how well (and if) the students can produce the new language – the

teacher can decide which of the stages to go to next. If the students cannot produce the new language at all, we will move to the explanation stage.